

ATTITUDE AND SKILLS TOWARD TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION OF SELECTED TEACHERS IN THE CITY OF MANILA AS BASIS FOR TECHNOLOGY ENHANCE EDUCATION

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Attitude and Skills Toward Technology Integration of Selected Teachers in the City of Manila as Basis for Technology Enhance Education

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Abstract

This study examines the attitudes and skills of secondary school teachers in Manila regarding technology integration, aiming to support the enhancement of educational methods with technology. A descriptive survey design was used to explore associations between teachers' demographic profiles and their perspectives on technology, focusing on both perceived ease of use and usefulness. The survey also assessed teachers' skills in planning, classroom management, instruction, and professional responsibilities in technology-enhanced settings. The findings show that younger teachers, particularly those with fewer than ten years of experience, tend to have more favorable attitudes toward technology integration. In contrast, older teachers and those with longer teaching tenures demonstrate a more cautious approach to technology use in the classroom. Teachers perceive technology as highly useful, especially in facilitating tasks and increasing productivity, though some are less convinced of its impact on instructional effectiveness. In terms of skills, the surveyed teachers exhibit proficiency in planning and preparation, often using available digital resources and adapting assignments to suit various student needs. Skills in creating an interactive classroom environment and leveraging technology for instructional purposes are moderately high, with teachers frequently using tools such as interactive whiteboards and digital assessments. However, technology is used primarily as a supplementary learning aid rather than as a core instructional resource, suggesting a need for further training on its integrative potential. The study concludes that professional development focused on practical applications of technology in education could help teachers better integrate digital tools into their core teaching methods. Insights from this study provide valuable guidance for curriculum developers, educational leaders, and policymakers in promoting more effective technology use among educators.

Keywords: *attitude, technology, integration, education*

Introduction

The primary figure in assisting students in gaining access to technological capabilities is the teacher. In order to enable students to communicate with one another in both their physical classroom and virtually through online learning environments, teachers should possess the necessary expertise in content and learning activity management. They should also endeavor to transform their classes from static to dynamic settings. In this instance, the teacher's role as one of several knowledge sources will change as they participate in the knowledge that has been created by others.

The teacher delivers high-quality educational outcomes by facilitating the learning process and providing timely feedback. She or he fosters a positive attitude toward lessons and provides an emotional and spiritual environment in the classroom, which strengthens the learners' necessary internal motivation. Nations all across the world have said that they want to make high-quality education more accessible to everyone. Even with free basic education, children's attendance remains a significant worry, indicating that it shouldn't be the only criterion used to determine eligibility for high-quality education.

The World Organization (2019) have identified gender inequality, security, natural disaster, economic status of the country, poverty, and proximity of the school as among the reasons for children's inability to attend school. Technology has been seen as a means of reducing the persistence of these enduring issues with getting access to high-quality education. These days, it is utilized to give education to kids that face geographic challenges; this type of instruction is called "online distance learning." Since technology is always present in our time, it is becoming more and more important to utilize it to engage children and teach them critical skills.

We use technology every day in many aspects of our lives. Computers, laptops, video games, smartphones, televisions, and even our automobiles are seen as "smart" devices. Today's educators must balance imparting traditional values and lessons from earlier generations with the difficulty of teaching digitally savvy kids who were exposed to technology almost from birth.

The development of information and communication technology (ICT) has significantly changed education in recent decades. People's lives are significantly impacted by this technology, both professionally and intellectually. In keeping with these changes, more emphasis needs to be placed on pedagogical digital competency when training teachers. This will enable educators to take full advantage of technology advancements and create innovative, engaging teaching-learning experiences for their students.

Modern classrooms are equipped with a wide range of technology, such as PCs, iPads, and smartboards. These technological tools have the ability to make teaching content much more effective, teach students new tech-handling skills, and make the material far more interesting and relevant for students in the future generation. But as history has shown us, new ideas, instruments, and solutions frequently do not function effectively in their initial iteration. Because many of the "old guard" are wary of changing what they have

been doing for their whole careers, especially in the lack of obvious alternatives supported by research, change may encounter opposition. Additionally, technology could have its own set of technical difficulties; for example, new components might not work together.

Since computers and laptops are older than the students themselves and have subpar hardware and software, the technology is far beyond its prime. Some schools try to address this issue by investing in the newest and greatest technology available, but without proper instruction and guidance, these devices are rapidly thrown away and their potential is squandered. Therefore, schools may be better able to make judgments about employing technology if they have a greater knowledge of the values and goals of the technologically savvy instructors.

In the classroom, educators have experimented with and integrated technology. Simple stereo speakers for playing music or a projector for writing assignments or notes on the board could be used, or more sophisticated networks of networked tablets, PCs, wireless display adapters, Bluetooth speakers, and other devices could be used to let students work together to create lessons in real time using tablet software tools. On the other hand, using technology just for its own reason presents a difficulty for educators.

Numerous instances exist where technology is employed in a way that deliberately impedes education. Some cutting-edge technologies might not work in the classroom because they are incompatible with existing technology, confusing, take too long to use effectively, or are just uninteresting to students (Gorder, 2008). In order to prevent technology from being either underutilized or abused in the absence of proper training and experience, I believe that the most crucial areas of concentration for successful technology integration in classrooms are teacher education and continuous professional development.

Teachers' computer and technological proficiency is a crucial component of this attribute. Teachers are expected to incorporate technology into the curriculum and classroom activities since many educational institutions have made significant expenditures in technology. Because of this, curricula in teacher education programs are being improved and redesigned to include more technology integration. This improvement comprises the know-how and abilities required for efficient technology use and integration.

Besides, teachers' attitudes and beliefs toward technology usage should result in a positive one. Therefore, teachers should be designated in such a way that besides knowing how to use technologies effectively

Research Questions

The study aims to determine the Attitude and Skills toward Technology Integration of Selected Teachers in the City of Manila as basis for Technology enhance Education. Specific question that the researcher aims to answer are thew following:

1. What is the demographic profile of the teachers in terms of the following?
 - 1.1. personal characteristic; and
 - 1.2. academic characteristics?
2. How do the personal and academic characteristics of teachers associate with their attitude towards technology?
3. How do the personal and academic characteristics of teachers associate with their skills towards technology?
4. What is the level of teacher's attitude toward technology integration?
5. What is the level of teacher skills toward technology integration?

Literature Review

Modern teaching methods now rely heavily on technological integration in the ever changing field of education. Digital tools, platforms, and resources may be used in the classroom to improve student learning, tailor instruction, and get them ready for a future that is driven by technology. However, instructors' attitudes and abilities have a big impact on how well technological integration works.

When it comes to whether and how instructors accept and use technological tools in the classroom, attitudes about technology integration are critical. While resistance or little use of technology may arise from a negative or cautious attitude, good attitudes can lead to enthusiastic adoption and creative use of technology. The perception of technology's utility, its usability, teachers' self-efficacy, and the degree of peer and school leadership support they receive are all factors that might affect their views about it.

Conversely, technology integration skills pertain to the practical talents that educators require in order to successfully integrate technology into their lesson plans. This covers more advanced skills like Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK), which entails knowing how to integrate technology with pedagogy and subject matter, in addition to fundamental digital literacy. Furthermore, the capacity to effectively navigate the benefits and difficulties associated with technology integration requires a strong foundation in classroom management, flexibility, and ongoing professional development.

Understanding the relationship between teachers' attitudes and abilities about technology integration is essential as schools embrace digital transformation more and more. With the ultimate goal of improving teaching effectiveness and student results, this introduction lays the groundwork for a discussion of the factors, difficulties, and best practices in promoting a constructive and knowledgeable attitude toward technology in education.

Scherer et al. (2020) discovered through a variety of research to identify the critical elements affecting educators' perceptions of

technology integration. Perceived utility, self-efficacy, and professional growth are found to be important determinants of positive attitudes in the study. The leadership and infrastructure of schools have a crucial role in facilitating the use of technology, as underscored by the meta-analysis.

Ertmer et al. (2021) the impact of administrative assistance, professional development, and technological availability on teachers' use of it in the classroom. Teachers who have more frequent professional development opportunities and better access to resources are more likely to successfully integrate technology into their lessons. The report also highlights how crucial it is that school administrators continue to support their efforts.

Inan and Lowther (2022) indicates that instructors are more willing to accept and use technology in the classroom if they have strong ideas about the benefits of technology for student learning. The study also discovers that continuing professional growth and past technological encounters have an impact on these attitudes.

Teo et al. (2021) investigates the contribution of both internal and external motivation on instructors' attempts to integrate technology. According to the study, extrinsic incentive such as pressure from the administration or external rewards is a weaker predictor of technology use than intrinsic motivation, which includes interest in technology and personal happiness. The study's qualitative element emphasizes how crucial it is to provide a nurturing atmosphere that encourages instructors' intrinsic drive.

Hinson and Bailey (2023) His research finds important obstacles such restricted technological availability, a dearth of possibilities for professional growth, and insufficient technical assistance. It also emphasizes, though, how important neighborhood activities and assistance are in overcoming these obstacles.

Wang et al. (2022) The association between teachers' perceptions of their own abilities, their views toward technology, and the actual usage of technology in the classroom is examined in this research. According to the research, favorable views toward technology and its use are significantly predicted by self-efficacy. According to the study, improving teachers' attitudes and sense of self-efficacy also requires professional growth.

Koh and Chai (2020) his study examines how the abilities and attitudes of teachers regarding technology can be improved through professional development programs that emphasize TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge). According to studies, teachers who receive focused professional development are far better able to incorporate technology into their lessons, which results in more favorable attitudes and more technology use.

Mumtaz and Siddiqui (2021) found out that Positive attitudes toward technology integration are more common among younger instructors and those with less experience in the classroom. Additionally, although the difference is not statistically significant, the study finds that female instructors are somewhat less confidence than their male colleagues when employing technology . .

Tondeur et al. (2020) found that both attitudes and abilities are markedly improved by focused professional development, especially when the training is practical and immediately applicable to classroom settings. The study also emphasizes how crucial peer cooperation and continuing assistance are to maintaining positive attitudes and skill development. .

Ertmer and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2022) The findings suggest that Technology integration is more frequent among instructors who have higher levels of self-efficacy because they are more likely to have favorable attitudes about technology. According to the study, fostering positive attitudes and self-efficacy also heavily depends on professional growth.

Methodology

Research Design

A quantitative approach was followed. Gerdes& Conn, 2001, p. 1 define quantitative methods are based in scientific discovery, the “notion among scholars that the traditional scientific method is the best, if not the only, legitimate way to conduct scholarly research” prevails So, the scientific community has developed clear guidelines and procedures for implementation of quantitative methods. Surveys may be used for descriptive, explanatory and exploratory research. A descriptive survey design was used. A survey is used to collect original data for describing a population too large to observe directly (Mouton 1996:232). A survey obtains information from a sample of people by means of self-report, that is, the people respond to a series of questions posed by the investigator (Polit & Hungler 1993:148). In this study the information was collected through self-administered questionnaires distributed personally to the subjects by the researcher.

A descriptive survey was selected because it provides an accurate portrayal or account of the characteristics, for example behaviour, opinions, abilities, beliefs, and knowledge of a particular individual, situation or group. This design was chosen to meet the objectives of the study, namely to determine the attitude and skills of teachers towards technology, its determinants, as basis for technology enhance education.

Respondents

The major purpose of this study was to integrate a worldwide series of studies related to attitude and skills toward technology integration

of selected teachers at the city of manila. These studies have been conducted for a variety of reasons, including, but not limited to, identify the changes that have occurred in the teachers experiencing technology education. To achieve the researcher's primary purpose, all previous studies on attitude and skills toward technology search were used as target studies.

The target population of the present study is the secondary teacher in the city of manila. Email was used to contact teachers who belonged to different school in the city of manila. Once the data collection was completed, a preliminary treatment of the data was carried out. Regarding the confidentiality of the answer of the participants, the survey was filled out anonymously guaranteeing the privacy of their data. They were also informed of the purpose of the investigation.

This study used the random sampling technique in the selection of respondents. It is a random selection of sampling units within the segments of the population with the most information on the characteristics of interest (Guarte & Barrios, 2004). The participating teachers were selected through an intentionally non-probabilistic sampling process. The sample of this study can be considered representative of the population of secondary teacher in the city of manila as it configured by participants belonging to the different areas of knowledge that articulate Philippine education system.

Instrument

I generated a survey tool with three parts. The first part was used to gather the personal and academic profile of the respondents. The second part was used to determine the respondents' attitude towards technology of which the items were adopted from the technology acceptance model of Ventakesh & Davis (2000). Item numbers 1–6 intend to measure the respondents' perceived usefulness of technology, whereas item numbers 7–12 intend to measure their perceived ease of use of technology.

A Likert scale was used to gather responses with 1 as Neither 2 as Slightly 3 as Quite 4 Extremely . The third part was used to determine the respondents' skills toward technology of which the item was adopted from Danielson four domain skills toward technology. Item 1 -5 intend to measure the Planning and Preparation, 6- 10 intend to measure the classroom environment, 11-15 intend to measure the Instruction and 16-20 intend to measure the Professional Responsibilities. A Likert scale was used to gather responses with 1 as Neither 2 as Slightly 3 as Quite 4 Extremely .

Procedure

Data were collected from the respondents through a paper and pen survey and online survey using Google Form. Research that gathered data through a survey refers to a collection of information from a sample of individuals through their responses to questions (Check & Schutt, 2012, as cited by Ponto, 2015). Responses were collected from the respondents within three weeks.

Data Analysis

The trial copy of Statistical Package for Social Science version 21 was used to analyze the personal and academic characteristics of the respondents. the frequency distribution and percentages were computed. The same software was used in determining the level of teachers' attitude towards technology and level of teacher skills toward technology integration practice by computing its mean and standard deviation.

Results and Discussion

Teacher Attitude Towards Technology Integration

The success of any initiatives to implement technology in an educational programmed depends strongly upon the support and attitudes of teacher educators involved. It has been suggested that if teachers believed or perceived proposed computer programmed as fulfilling neither their own or their students' needs, they are not likely to attempt to introduce technology into their teaching and learning. Among the factors that affect the successful use of computers in the classroom are teachers' attitudes towards computers (Huang and Liaw, 2005).

Teacher Skills Towards Technology Integration

Educators need to understand some basics about technology and that it is not a be-all-end-all solution to everything in a classroom. Technology can help teachers differentiate and provide new experiences for their students. Technology can also help students better understand a concept and provide extra help for them.

Educators need to start with good pedagogy and lesson objectives and activities and then look for technology that can enhance those lessons, improve teaching and learning, and help students learn.

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the summary of the respondents' profile. Data revealed that majority of the respondents are within the age range of 41-50 (58%), but only a few (2%) are between 51–60 years of age. Majority of them have been serving the school as a faculty member for less than 10 years (40%). Lastly, the majority of the respondents are handling college/ universities (56%), and a few teaches in Junior High (18%).

Table 1. *Profile of the Respondents*

	Determinants	frequency	Percentage
Personal Characteristic Age	20-30	6	12%
	31-40	14	28%
	41-50	29	58%
	51-60	1	2%
Academic Characteristics Years of Stay	0-10	20	40%
	11-20	17	34%
	21-30	13	26%
Grade Level Assignment	Junior High	9	
	Senior High	13	18%
	College/Universities	28	26%
			56%

Level of teachers Attitude toward technology integration on the Two Dimensions

To determine the teacher's attitude in two dimensions such as perceive ease of use and perceived usefulness.

Rubric scoring was use to interpret the teachers Attitude toward technology integration was also developed by the researcher and validated by the experts.

Dimension 1: Perceived ease of Use

Table 2. *Teachers Attitude toward Technology Integration*

Indicator	Mean	Standard deviation	Interpretation
Using technology in my job would enable me to accomplish tasks more quickly	4.820	.3881	Highly Favorable
Using technology would improve my job performance	4.700	.4629	Highly Favorable
Using technology in my job would increase my productivity	4.760	.4314	Highly Favorable
Using technology would enhance my effectiveness on the job.	4.580	.4986	Moderately High favorable
Using technology would make it easier to do my job.	4.700	.4629	Highly Favorable
I would find technology useful in my job.	4.640	.5980	Highly Favorable

Table 2 shows the summary of teachers' responses pertaining to their attitude towards technology in dimension 1 perceived ease of use. Data in Table 2 revealed that item number 1 has the highest mean ($\bar{x}=4.820$, $\sigma\bar{x}=.3881$), indicating that majority of the respondents strongly agree that technology in the form of any computer applications is useful for them as teachers. In contrast, Item number 4 has the lowest mean ($\bar{x}=4.580$, $\sigma\bar{x}=.4986$), indicating that respondents have various perception whether Using technology would enhance their effectiveness on the job.

Dimension 2: Perceived Usefulness

Table 3. *Teachers Attitude toward Technology Integration*

Indicator	Mean	Standard deviation	Interpretation
Learning to operate different technology would be easy for me	4.300	.4629	Moderately High favorable
I would find it easy to get this technology to do what I want it to do	4.360	.4849	Moderately High favorable
My interaction with the technology would be clear and understandable.	4.240	.5555	Moderately High favorable
It would be easy for me to become skillful and at using technology.	4.300	.5803	Moderately High favorable
I would find technology would be clear and understandable	4.420	.4986	Moderately High favorable
I would find technology easy to use.	4.420	.4986	Moderately High favorable

Table 3 shows the summary of teachers' responses pertaining to their attitude towards technology in dimension 2 perceived usefulness. Data in Table 3 revealed that item number 6 has the highest mean ($\bar{x}=4.420$, $\sigma\bar{x}=.4986$), indicating that majority of the respondents strongly agree that technology would find easy to use. In contrast, Item number 3 has the lowest mean ($\bar{x}=4.240$, $\sigma\bar{x}=.5555$), indicating that respondents have various perception whether Using technology would be clear and understandable.

Level of teachers Skills toward technology integration on the Four Dimensions

To determine the teacher's skills in four dimensions such as Planning and Preparation, the Classroom Environment, Instruction and Professional Responsibilities.

Rubric scoring was use to interpret the teachers skills toward technology integration was also developed by the researcher and validated by the experts.

Dimension 1: Planning and FavorableTable 4. *Teachers Skills toward Technology Integration*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Creates assignments appropriate to the technology abilities of my students.	4.640	.4849	Expert
Uses digital resources provided by the district, including online productivity tools, content management systems, e-textbooks, online reference sources, video-streaming sites, and learning systems.	4.460	.5035	Master
Designs learning activities that use available technology, including laptops, tablets, computer labs, and interactive whiteboards	4.540	.6131	Master
Uses digital resources to differentiate instruction, including using devices for my students with special needs, such as computer activities and online materials suited to different reading abilities or learning preferences.	4.660	.4785	Expert
Assesses technology production to my student work when applicable.	4.700	.4629	Expert

Table 4 shows the summary of teachers' responses pertaining to their skills towards technology in dimension 1 Planning and Favorable. Data in Table 4 revealed that item number 5 has the highest mean ($\bar{x}=4.700$ $\sigma\bar{x}=.4629$), indicating that majority of the respondents strongly agree that assess technology production to their students work when applicable. In contrast, Item number 2 has the lowest mean ($\bar{x}=4.460$, $\sigma\bar{x}=.5035$), indicating that respondents have various perception whether they used digital resources provided by the district, including online productivity tools, content management systems, e-textbooks, online reference sources, video-streaming sites, and learning systems or not.

Dimension 2: The Classroom EnvironmentTable 5. *Teachers Skills toward Technology Integration*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Demonstrates a positive attitude toward educational technology during class	4.460	.6764	Expert
Uses technology to help students "publish" their work online for other students, parents, and the public to view, following district safety and privacy rules	4.360	.6312	Master
Uses technology to facilitate collaborative creation and peer editing of student work.	4.440	.6110	Master
Creates rules for technology use in the classroom, including rules regarding the use of personally owned technology devices, such as cell phones.	4.580	.5379	Master
Monitors student technology use and responds to misuse if it occurs.	4.480	.5436	Master

Table 5 shows the summary of teachers' responses pertaining to their skills towards technology in dimension 2 The Classroom Environment. Data in Table 5 revealed that item number 4 has the highest mean ($\bar{x}=4.580$ $\sigma\bar{x}=.5379$), indicating that majority of the respondents strongly agree that for technology use in the classroom, including rules regarding the use of personally owned technology devices, such as cell phones. In contrast, Item number 2 has the lowest mean ($\bar{x}=4.360$, $\sigma\bar{x}=.6312$), indicating that respondents have various perception whether they uses technology to help students "publish" their work online for other students, parents, and the public to view, following district safety and privacy rules or not.

Dimension 3: InstructionsTable 6. *Teachers Skills toward Technology Integration*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Uses the classroom sound amplification system, if available	4.580	.4986	Master
Uses technology to create and project visual images and video that help explain content and concepts	4.640	.4849	Expert
Uses the interactive whiteboard in ways that engage students. These include student use of the board, gaming applications, actions based on student responses, and polling.	4.580	.4986	Master
Encourages students to use online resources to answer questions and explore concepts during class and teaches search and information evaluation strategies.	4.400	.8571	Master
Uses technology to help students produce their own work (writing, designing, creating) and meet the instructional goals of the lesson.	4.500	.6776	Master

Table 6 shows the summary of teachers' responses pertaining to their skills towards technology in dimension 3 Instruction. Data in Table 6 revealed that item number 2 has the highest mean ($\bar{x}=4.640$ $\sigma\bar{x}=.4849$), indicating that majority of the respondents strongly agree that Uses technology to create and project visual images and video that help them explain content and concepts In contrast, Item number 4 has the lowest mean ($\bar{x}=4.400$, $\sigma\bar{x}=.8571$), indicating that respondents have various perception whether Encourages students to use online resources to answer questions and explore concepts during class and teaches search and information evaluation strategies

or not.

Dimension 4: Professional Responsibilities

Table 7. *Teachers Skills toward Technology Integration*

Indicator	Mean	Standard deviation	Interpretation
Uses an online grading and reporting system to maintain information on student completion rates and shares this information through student and parent portals in a consistent and timely manner	4.540	.5035	Master
Uses an online grading system portal to inform students and parents of upcoming assignments, projects, and assessments well ahead of the date due.	4.740	.4849	Expert
Provides current classroom information to students and parents on the district website.	4.380	.6667	Master
Keeps students and parents informed using online communication tools such as e-mail, blogs, and social networks on a regular basis.	4.560	.5771	Master
Uses collaborative online tools to communicate and work with colleagues	4.640	.4849	Expert

Table 7 shows the summary of teachers’ responses pertaining to their skills towards technology in dimension 4 Professional Responsibilities. Data in Table 6 revealed that item number 2 has the highest mean (\bar{x} =4.740 $\sigma_{\bar{x}}$ =.4849), indicating that majority of the respondents strongly agree that Using an online grading system portal to inform students and parents of upcoming assignments, projects, and assessments well ahead of the date due. In contrast, Item number 3 has the lowest mean (\bar{x} =4.380, $\sigma_{\bar{x}}$ =.6667), indicating that respondents have various perception whether they Provides current classroom information to students and parents on the district website or not.

Table 8. *Significant difference in the Profile of Teachers Attitude and Skills toward Technology integration*

Profile	Chi-square, χ^2	df	p - value	Decision
Age	35.920	3	0.000	Reject Ho
Years of Stay	1.480	2	0.477	Fail to Reject Ho
Grade level Assignment	12.040	2	0.002	Reject Ho

* Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table showed that there was a statistically significant difference in the profile of age, $\chi^2= 35.920$, $p = 0.000$ and grade level assignment $\chi^2= 12.040$, $p = 0.002$ a , thus Ho is rejected. There is a significant difference in the Profile of Teachers Attitude and Skills toward Technology integration. However, the table also revealed that the p value for years of stay ($\chi^2= 1.480$, $p = 0.477$), age is greater than 0.or level of significance, therefore, fail to reject Ho. This implies that there is no significant difference in the Profile of Teachers Attitude and Skills toward Technology integration.

Significance difference in the Barriers in Teacher’s Attitude toward technology Integration

Table 9. *Perceived ease of Use*

Indicators	Age		Years Of Stay		Grade Level Assignment	
	Chi-square, χ^2	P - value	Chi - square, χ^2	P - value	Chi - square, χ^2	P - value
1. Using technology in my job would enable me to accomplish tasks more quickly	23.135	.000	5.910	.525	2.552	.279
2. Using technology would improve my job performance.	16.495	.001	.524	.770	.324	.850
3. Using technology in my job would increase my productivity	17.762	.000	.777	.678	7.949	.850
4. Using technology would enhance my effectiveness on the job.	7.025	.071	2.820	.244	2.545	.280
5. Using technology would make it easier to do my job	12.147	.007	.524	.770	3.782	.151
6. I would find technology useful in my job.	21.815	.001	6.571	.160	2.792	.593

Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 9 revealed that in the profile of Age in terms of Perceived ease of use item number 1 $\chi^2= 23.135$, $p = 0.000$, item number 2 $\chi^2= 16.495$, $p = 0.001$, item number 3 $\chi^2= 17.762$, $p = 0.000$, item number 4 $\chi^2= 7.025$, $p = 0.071$ item number 5 $\chi^2= 12.147$, $p = 0.007$ and item number 6 2 $\chi^2=21.815$, $p = 0.001$, thus Ho is rejected. There is a significant difference in the perceived ease of use based on age. Respondents in different age group perceives using technology would not be easy. Also, table show that in the profile of years of stay in terms of perceived ease of use item number 1 $\chi^2= 5.910$, $p = 0.525$, item number 2 $\chi^2= 0.524$, $p = 0.770$, item number 3 $\chi^2= 2.820$, $p = 0.244$, item number 4 $\chi^2= 2.820$, $p = 0.244$, item number 5 $\chi^2=0.524$, $p = 0.770$, and item number 6 $\chi^2= 6.571$, $p = 0.160$ is greater than 0.or level of significance, therefore, fail to reject Ho. This implies that there is no significant difference in the perceived

ease of use based on years of stay. Respondents in different years of stay perceives learning using technology would be easy.

Table also show in profile of grade level assignment in terms of perceived ease of use item number 1 $\chi^2= 2.552$, $p = 0.279$, item number 2 $\chi^2= 0.324$, $p = 0.850$, item number 3 $\chi^2= 7.949$, $p= 0.850$, item number 4 $\chi^2= 2.545$, $p = 0.280$, item number 5 $\chi^2=3.782$, $p = 0.151$, and item number 6 $\chi^2=2.792$, $p = 0.593$ is greater than 0.or level of significance, therefore, fail to reject Ho. This implies that there is no significant difference in the perceived ease of use based on grade level assignment. Respondents in different grade level assignment perceives learning using technology would be easy.

Table 10. *Perceived Usefulness*

Indicators	Age		Years Of Stay		Grade Level Assignment	
	Chi-square, χ^2	P - value	Chi - square, χ^2	P - value	Chi - square, χ^2	P - value
1. Learning to operate different technology would be easy for me	3.882	.274	.469	.791	2.731	.255
2. I would find it easy to get this technology to do what I want it to do	6.170	.104	3.322	.190	5.521	.053
3. My interaction with the technology would be clear and understandable.	7.111	.311	7.348	.119	6.257	.181
4. It would be easy for me to become skillful and at using technology	7.965	.241	11.625	.020	7.114	.130
5. I would find technology easy to use. would find technology would be clear and understandable	10.843	.017	1.541	.463	0.830	.660
6. I would find technology useful in my job.	5.906	.116	1.547	.463	2.248	.325

Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 10 revealed that in the profile of Age in terms of Perceived Usefulness item number 1 $\chi^2= 3.882$, $p = 0.274$, item number 2 $\chi^2= 6.170$, $p = 0.104$, item number 3 $\chi^2= 7.111$, $p = 0.311$, item number 4 $\chi^2= 7.965$, $p = 0.241$ and item number 6 $\chi^2=5.906$, $p = 0.116$, is greater than 0.or level of significance, therefore, fail to reject Ho. This implies that there is no significant difference in the perceived usefulness based on age. However, item number 5 $\chi^2= 10.843$, $p = 0.017$, thus Ho is rejected. There is a significant difference in the perceived usefulness based on age. Also, table show that in the profile of years of stay in terms of perceived usefulness item number 1 $\chi^2= 0.469$, $p = 0.791$, item number 2 $\chi^2= 3.322$, $p = 0.190$, item number 3 $\chi^2= 7.348$, $p = 0.119$, item number 5 $\chi^2=1.541$, $p = 0.463$, and item number 6 $\chi^2= 1.547$, $p = 0.463$ is greater than 0.or level of significance, therefore, fail to reject Ho. This implies that there is no significant difference in the perceived usefulness based on years of stay. However, item number 4 $\chi^2= 11.625$, $p = 0.020$, thus Ho is rejected. There is a significant difference in the perceived usefulness based on yeast of stay.

Table also show in profile of grade level assignment in terms of perceived usefulness item number 1 $\chi^2= 2.731$, $p = 0.255$, item number 3 $\chi^2=6.257$, $p = 0.181$, item number 4 $\chi^2= 7.114$, $p = 0.130$, item number 5 $\chi^2=0.830$, $p = 0.660$, and item number 6 $\chi^2=2.248$, $p = 0.325$ is greater than 0.or level of significance, therefore, fail to reject Ho. This implies that there is no significant difference in the perceived ease of use based on grade level assignment. However, item number 2 $\chi^2= 5.521$, $p = 0.053$, thus Ho is rejected. There is a significant difference in the perceived usefulness based on grade level assignment

Significance difference in the Barriers in Teacher’s Skills toward technology Integration

Table 11. *Planning and Preparation*

Indicators	Age		Years Of Stay		Grade Level Assignment	
	Chi-square, χ^2	P - value	Chi - square, χ^2	P - value	Chi - square, χ^2	P - value
1. Creates assignments appropriate to the technology abilities of my students.	15.851	.001	.898	.638	2.719	.257
2. Uses digital resources provided by the district, including online productivity tools, content management systems, e-textbooks, online reference sources, video-streaming sites, and learning systems	15.851	.001	2.348	.309	8.568	.014
3. Designs learning activities that use available technology, including laptops, tablets, computer labs, and interactive whiteboards	19.182	.004	15.638	.004	5.365	.252
4. Uses digital resources to differentiate instruction, including using devices for my students with special needs, such as computer activities and online materials suited to different reading abilities or learning preferences.	15.860	.001	1.158	.561	3.206	.201
5. Assesses technology production to my student work when applicable.	22.414	.000	4.545	.103	8.383	.015

Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 11 revealed that in the profile of Age in terms of Planning and Preparation item number 1 $\chi^2= 15.851$, $p = 0.001$, item number 2 $\chi^2= 15.851$, $p = 0.001$, item number 3 $\chi^2= 19.182$, $p = 0.004$, item number 4 $\chi^2= 15.860$, $p = 0.001$ and item number 5 $\chi^2= 22.414$, $p = 0.000$ thus H_0 is rejected. There is a significant difference in the Planning and Preparation based on age.

Also, table show that in the profile of years of stay in terms of Planning and Preparation item number 1 $\chi^2= 0.898$, $p = 0.638$, item number 2 $\chi^2= 2.348$, $p = 0.3.9$, , item number 4 $\chi^2= 1.158$, $p= 0.561$, and item number 5 $\chi^2=4.545$, $p = 0.103$, is greater than 0.or level of significance, therefore, fail to reject H_0 . This implies that there is no significant difference in the Planning and Preparation based on years of stay. However, item number 3 $\chi^2= 15.638$, $p = 0.004$ thus H_0 is rejected. There is a significant difference in the Planning and Preparation based on years of stay. Table also show in profile of grade level assignment in terms of Planning and Preparation item number 1 $\chi^2= 2.719$, $p = 0.257$, , item number 3 $\chi^2= 5.365$, $p = 0.252$, and item number 4 $\chi^2= 3.206$, $p = 0.201$, is greater than 0.or level of significance, therefore, fail to reject H_0 . This implies that there is no significant difference in Planning and Preparation based on grade level assignment. However, item number 2 $\chi^2=8.568$, $p = 0.014$ and item number 5 $\chi^2=8.383$, $p = 0.015$ thus H_0 is rejected. There is a significant difference in the Planning and Preparation based on grade level assignment.

Table 12. *The Classroom Environment*

Indicators	Age		Years Of Stay		Grade Level Assignment	
	Chi-square, χ^2	P - value	Chi - square, χ^2	P - value	Chi - square, χ^2	P - value
1. Demonstrates a positive attitude toward educational technology during class.	18.277	.006	18.403	.001	5.763	.218
2. Uses technology to help students "publish" their work online for other students, parents, and the public to view, following district safety and privacy rules.	13.022	.043	10.693	.030	3.517	.475
3. Uses technology to facilitate collaborative creation and peer editing of student work.	22.207	.001	6.276	.179	5.364	.252
4. Creates rules for technology use in the classroom, including rules regarding the use of personally owned technology devices, such as cell phones.	22.310	.001	12.130	.016	8.031	.050
5. Monitors student technology use and responds to misuse if it occurs.	27.136	.000	4.479	.345	9.400	.052

Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 12 revealed that in the profile of Age in terms of The Classroom Environment item number 1 $\chi^2= 18.277$, $p = 0.006$, item number 2 $\chi^2= 13.022$, $p = 0.043$, item number 3 $\chi^2= 22.207$, $p = 0.001$, item number 4 $\chi^2= 22.310$, $p = 0.001$ and item number 5 $\chi^2= 27.136$, $p = 0.000$ thus H_0 is rejected. There is a significant difference in the classroom environment based on age.

Also, table shows that in the profile of years of stay in terms of The Classroom Environment item number 1 $\chi^2= 18.403$, $p = 0.001$, item number 2 $\chi^2= 10.693$, $p = 0.030$, and item number 4 $\chi^2= 12.130$, $p = 0.016$ thus H_0 is rejected. There is a significant difference in the classroom environment based on years of stay. However item number 3 $\chi^2= 6.276$, $p = 0.179$ and item number 5 $\chi^2= 4.479$, $p = 0.345$ is greater than 0.or level of significance, therefore, fail to reject H_0 . This implies that there is no significant difference in the classroom environment based on years of stay.

Table also show in profile of grade level assignment in terms of the classroom environment item number 1 $\chi^2= 5.763$, $p = 0.218$, , item number 2 $\chi^2= 3.517$, $p = 0.475$, and item number 3 $\chi^2= 5.364$, $p = 0.252$, is greater than 0.or level of significance, therefore, fail to reject H_0 . This implies that there is no significant difference in the classroom environment based on grade level assignment. However, item number 4 $\chi^2=8.031$, $p = 0.050$ and item number 5 $\chi^2=9.400$, $p = 0.052$ thus H_0 is rejected. There is a significant difference in the classroom environment based on grade level assignment.

Table 13 revealed that in the profile of Age in terms of The Classroom Environment item number 1 $\chi^2= 18.277$, $p = 0.006$, item number 2 $\chi^2= 13.022$, $p = 0.043$, item number 3 $\chi^2= 22.207$, $p = 0.001$, item number 4 $\chi^2= 22.310$, $p = 0.001$ and item number 5 $\chi^2= 27.136$, $p = 0.000$ thus H_0 is rejected. There is a significant difference in the classroom environment based on age.

Also, table shows that in the profile of years of stay in terms of The Classroom Environment item number 1 $\chi^2= 18.403$, $p = 0.001$, item number 2 $\chi^2= 10.693$, $p = 0.030$, and item number 4 $\chi^2= 12.130$, $p = 0.016$ thus H_0 is rejected. There is a significant difference in the classroom environment based on years of stay. However item number 3 $\chi^2= 6.276$, $p = 0.179$ and item number 5 $\chi^2= 4.479$, $p = 0.345$ is greater than 0.or level of significance, therefore, fail to reject H_0 . This implies that there is no significant difference in the classroom environment based on years of stay.

Table also show in profile of grade level assignment in terms of the classroom environment item number 1 $\chi^2= 5.763$, $p = 0.218$, , item number 2 $\chi^2= 3.517$, $p = 0.475$, and item number 3 $\chi^2= 5.364$, $p = 0.252$, is greater than 0.or level of significance, therefore, fail to reject H_0 . This implies that there is no significant difference in the classroom environment based on grade level assignment. However, item number 4 $\chi^2=8.031$, $p = 0.050$ and item number 5 $\chi^2=9.400$, $p = 0.052$ thus H_0 is rejected. There is a significant difference in the classroom environment based on grade level assignment.

Table 13. *Instructions*

Indicators	Age		Years Of Stay		Grade Level Assignment	
	Chi-square, χ^2	P - value	Chi - square, χ^2	P - value	Chi - square, χ^2	P - value
1. Uses the classroom sound amplification system, if available.	16.853	.001	5.453	.050	2.203	.332
2. Uses technology to create and project visual images and video that help explain content and concepts.	15.851	.001	16.496	.000	2.719	.257
3. Uses the interactive whiteboard in ways that engage students, including student use of the board, gaming applications, actions based on student responses, and polling.	16.853	.001	5.453	.050	2.203	.332
4. Encourages students to use online resources to answer questions and explore concepts during class and teaches search and information evaluation strategies.	20.521	.002	13.601	.009	5.905	.206
5. Uses technology to help students produce their own work (writing, designing, creating) and meet the instructional goals of the lesson.	21.695	.001	23.977	.000	8.153	.086

Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 14 revealed that in the profile of Age in terms of The Professional Responsibilities item number 1 $\chi^2= 8.004$, $p = 0.046$, item number 2 $\chi^2= 9.213$, $p = 0.027$, item number 3 $\chi^2=12.975$, $p = 0.043$, item number 4 $\chi^2= 18.138$, $p = 0.006$ and item number 5 $\chi^2= 15.851$, $p = 0.001$ thus H_0 is rejected. There is a significant difference in the Professional responsibilities based on age.

Table 14. *Professional Responsibilities*

Indicators	Age		Years Of Stay		Grade Level Assignment	
	Chi-square, χ^2	P - value	Chi - square, χ^2	P - value	Chi - square, χ^2	P - value
1. Uses an online grading and reporting system to maintain information on student completion rates and shares this information through student and parent portals in a consistent and timely manner.	8.004	.046	4.456	.108	1.161	.560
2. Uses an online grading system portal to inform students and parents of upcoming assignments, projects, and assessments well ahead of the due date.	9.213	.027	.898	.638	5.871	.053
3. Provides current classroom information to students and parents on the district website.	12.974	.043	16.261	.003	5.461	.243
4. Keeps students and parents informed using online communication tools such as e-mail, blogs, and social networks on a regular basis.	18.138	.006	12.163	.016	4.204	.379
5. Uses collaborative online tools to communicate and work with colleagues.	15.851	.001	.898	.638	2.719	.257

Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Also, table shows that in the profile of years of stay in terms of The Professional Responsibilities item number 1 $\chi^2= 4.456$, $p = 0.108$, item number 2 $\chi^2= 0.898$, $p = 0.638$ and item number 5 $\chi^2= 0.898$, $p = 0.638$, is greater than 0.05 level of significance, therefore, fail to reject H_0 . This implies that there is no significant difference in the Professional Responsibilities based on years of stay. However, item number 3 $\chi^2=16.261$, $p = 0.003$ and item number 4 $\chi^2= 12.163$, $p = 0.016$, thus H_0 is rejected. There is a significant difference in the Professional responsibilities based on years of stay.

Table also show in profile of grade level assignment in terms of Professional Responsibilities item number 1 $\chi^2= 1.161$, $p = 0.560$, item number 3 $\chi^2= 5.461$, $p = 0.243$ and item number 4 $\chi^2= 4.204$, $p = 0.379$, and, item number 5 $\chi^2= 2.719$, $p = 0.257$ is greater than 0.05 level of significance, therefore, fail to reject H_0 . This implies that there is no significant difference in the Professional Responsibilities based on years of stay. However, item number 2 $\chi^2=5.871$, $p = 0.053$ thus H_0 is rejected. There is a significant difference in the Professional responsibilities based on grade level assignment

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The findings in this study suggest that the years of stay of the teachers as the respondents has the most significant association with their attitude towards technology. This can be attribute to the fact that majority of the respondents who participated in the study are between zero to ten years of stay

The findings in this study suggest that the age of the teachers as the respondents has the most significant association with their skills towards technology. This can be attributed to the fact that majority of the respondents who participated in the study are between twenty to thirty years old.

The association of teachers' attitude towards technology and their technology integration practice has been proven to be true in this study. However, it is only their perceived ease of use of technology that was found to be significantly associated with using technology as a teaching tool and a learning tool as indicators of their technology integration practice

This study reveals that teachers had been using technology more as a learning tool. A qualitative study involving classroom observations, document analysis, and interview would provide a better explanation of how technology is integrated in the classroom.

Based on the findings of the study conclusion derived the following are hereby recommended:

With some modifications, this study can be implemented in other educational settings and cultures. Also, the methodology designed for this study may be used to repeat this study over time or with a larger sample size.

Since the current study focused only on teacher's attitude and skills of the teachers toward technology integration future studies may consider studying student's attitudes about technology in the same setting to provide more of an accurate portrayal of the classroom experience.

Findings of this study can inform curriculum development, teacher education programs, and outreach programs as to the types of technology and effective implementation in terms of TPACK for engaging students

The findings may provide schools, community colleges and universities, as well as graduate level educators, educational leaders and educational organizations moving to technology-driven learning platforms with valuable information on the humanistic aspect of designing strategies, techniques and support structures to assist educators in effectively and successfully embracing the innovation.

References

- Alharbi, S., & Drew, S. (2014). Using the technology acceptance model in understanding academics' behavioural intention to use learning management systems. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 5(1), 143–155. Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/f996/9c881e6228723b0e6975abc190b30926d1ef.pdf>
- Bana, C., Romasame, J. R., & Cristobal, E. (2016). Gender disaggregated analysis of the e-learning readiness state of students in a public higher education institution. Retrieved from http://www.elearningap.com/eLAP2015/Proceedings/02_18_Gender.pdf
- Bates, T. (2014, December 10). A short history of educational technology. *Online Learning and Distance Education Resources*. Retrieved from <http://bit.ly/2CZlq6F>
- Bang, E., & Luft, J. (2014). Secondary science teachers' use of technology in the classroom during their first 5 years. *Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education*, 29(4), 118–216. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21532974.2013.10784715>
- Cavas, B., Cavas, P., Karaoglan, B., & Kisla, T. (2009). A study on science teachers' attitudes toward information and communication technologies in education. *TOJET: The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 8(2). Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED505935>
- DeCoito, I., & Richardson, T. (2018). Teachers and technology: Present practice and future directions. *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 18(2). Retrieved from <https://www.citejournal.org/volume-18/issue-2-18/science/teachersand-technology-present-practice-and-future-directions>
- Elkaseh, A. M., Wong, K. W., & Fung, C. C. (2016). Perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of social media for e-learning in Libyan higher education: A structural equation modeling analysis. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 6(3), 192–199. doi:10.7763/IJET.2016.V6.683
- Fathema, N., Shannon, D., & Ross, M. (2015). Expanding the technology acceptance model (TAM) to examine faculty use of learning management systems (LMSs) in higher education institutions. *Journal of Online Learning & Teaching*, 11(2), 210–232. Retrieved from http://jolt.merlot.org/Vol11No2/Fathema_0615.pdf
- Guarte, J. M., & Barrios, E. B. (2004). Estimation under purposive sampling. *Communications in Statistics—Simulation and Computation*, 35(2), 277–284. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610910600591610>
- Hooper, D., Coughlan, J., & Mullen, M. (2008). Structural equation modelling: Guidelines for determining model fit. *Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods*, 6(1), 53–60. Retrieved from <http://bit.ly/2WQvDOG>
- Howley, A., Wood, L., & Hough, B. (2011). Rural elementary school teachers' technology integration. *Journal of Research in Rural Education*, 26(9), 1–13. Retrieved from <http://jrre.vmhost.psu.edu/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/26-9.pdf>
- Hox, J. J., & Bechger, T. M. (1998). An introduction to structural equation modeling. *Family Science Review*, 11, 354–373. Retrieved

from <http://bit.ly/33Lp2co>

Manikandan, S. (2011). Frequency distribution. *Journal of Pharmacology & Pharmacotherapeutics*, 2(1), 54–56. doi:10.4103/0976-500X.77120

Mikropoulos, T. A., Sampson, D. G., Nikopoulos, A., & Pintelas, P. (2014). The evolution of educational technology based on a bibliometric study. In *Research on e-Learning and ICT in Education* (pp. 15-24). Springer, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-6501-0_2

Morales, H. M. (2015). Information and communication technology (ICT) integration model of instructional design: Its effectiveness. In E. Gorgon, J. Solana, O. Monforte, T. Tolentino, C. de Mesa, E. Habijan, & E. Libranda (Eds.), *R2A in Calabarzon: Reflection, research, action* (Vol. 2, pp. 129–146). Retrieved from <http://bit.ly/2pmwOGT>

Meigs, R. (2010). The development and validation of technology integration matrix questionnaire (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Baker University, USA. Retrieved from https://www.bakeru.edu/images/pdf/SOE/EdD_Theses/Meigs_Russell.pdf

Mustafina, A. (2016). Teachers' attitudes toward technology integration in a Kazakhstani secondary school. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science*, 2(2), 322–332. Retrieved from <https://ijres.net/index.php/ijres/article/view/112>

Nueva, M. G. (2019). Filipino teachers' attitude towards technology — Its determinants and association with technology integration practice. De La Salle Santiago Zobel School, Philippines.

Panda, S. (2017). Educational technology: Historical developments. Retrieved from <https://edtech2socialstudies.wordpress.com/2018/02/23/educational-technology-2/>

Pickens, J. (2005). Attitudes and perceptions. *Organizational Behavior in Health Care*, 43–76. Retrieved from <http://bit.ly/2P6sISA>

Pittman, T., & Gaines, T. (2015). Technology integration in third, fourth, and fifth-grade classrooms in a Florida school district. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 63(4), 539–554. doi:10.1007/s11423-015-9391-8

Ponto, J. (2015). Understanding and evaluating survey research. *Journal of the Advanced Practitioner in Oncology*, 6(2), 168–171. Retrieved from <http://bit.ly/2oT9gZc>

Ruggiero, D., & Mong, C. J. (2015). The teacher technology integration experience: Practice and reflection in the classroom. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, 14, 161–178. Retrieved from <http://www.jite.org/documents/Vol14/JITEv14ResearchP161-178Ruggiero0958.pdf>

Ruman, M., & Prakasha, G. (2017). Application of technology integration matrix (TIM) in teaching and learning of secondary schools science subjects. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 22(12), 24–26. Retrieved from <http://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jhss/papers/Vol.%2022%20Issue12/Version-9/D2212092426.pdf>

Saettler, P. (2004). *The evolution of American educational technology*. Connecticut: Information Age Publishing. Retrieved from <http://bit.ly/2tj7qGz>

Semerci, A., & Aydin, M. (2018). Examining high school teachers' attitudes toward ICT use in education.

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